
Comparative assessment of Green Rating Systems for Sustainable Buildings –An Overview

Ar. Abhinav Chaturvedi

Research Scholar –School of Architecture and Design, Manipal University Jaipur
(Working as :- Additional Principal , NIMS School of Architecture and Planning, Jaipur)

Guide :- Dr. (Prof.) Madhura Yadav .

Director , School of Architecture and Design , Manipal University Jaipur

Introduction :-

With Rapid rise in Population and to meet the future development goals , whole world is moving very fast in the direction of Rapid Industrialization. Every country is focusing on growth and maximum industrialization in order to win the race of the development. But this process creates a climatic imbalance of the existing climatic condition .With the increase in the concentration of the Green Houses gases and consequent global warming . The shift is observed in the predefined standards of Climate and this phenomenon is called as **Climate Change** and it is the greatest threat of 21 Century . The common observations of climate change are seen across the world that are :- the average temperature is rising , polar caps are melting and sea level is rising because of the same.

President of United States , Mr. Barack Obama presented his views in Paris – United Nations Conference (**Obama**, 2015) climate change is the most important parameter at the moment as it will define the contours of this century more dramatically perhaps than the other. According to (**Obama**, 2015) for United States ,Climate Change is the top most priority as no Nation weather it is large and small , is immune to the effects of climate change as he expressed “ even we somehow put the break on emission , climate change would still make an impact on our world for years to come. (**Obama**, 2015)expressed that if we could not act on time now , it will be too late for our future generations and they will curse the present generation for creating this mess.

Effects of Climate Change in India:-

In **India** climate change is already showing its presence .According to the report on climate change (Gupta J. , 16 June 2020)The average temperature of India rises by around 0.7 degree Celsius during 1901-2018 and will further rise to around 4.4 degree Celsius between 2070 – 2090 . The similar temperature variation is observed on the sea surface and the temperature rise of 1 degree is observed during 1951 – 2015 .Sea level is rising because of the same (

aprox 3.3mm per year. Further this also leads to uneven season of monsoon and which give rise to the draught situation in some of the monsoon depended areas.

According to the documentary movie (Discovery, 2020) the year 2010 to 2019 series of events are showing all the basic symptoms of climate change in different areas of India and these are as follows :-

- 1) **Bad Air Quality** :- According to (Discovery, 2020) in 2017 Air pollution had killed 1.2 million people across India . More than 70% of the country's electricity is generated from coal power is one of the major cause of the air pollution. In October 2019 - Delhi is declared as the most polluted city in the world and according to a survey it was found that because of the same more then 40% of the residents of Delhi would like to migrate from Delhi. More then 50% of the children in Delhi suffered with lungs disorder because of this inferior air quality. According to the survey out of 22 Most polluted cities in the world , 13 are from India.
- 2) **Rising Temperature** :- On 20th June 2019 , Temperature of Delhi rises to the record 48 degree centigrade .The met department declared the temperature “ Cole Red”. The surveys are depicting that the average temperature is rising and will continue to rise further.
- 3) **Draught Condition in Rajasthan** :- State like Rajasthan , totally depended on Monsoon rain for cultivation and drinking Water (Discovery, 2020). Due to change in weather conditions some areas of the state are receiving less then normal condition therefore some areas is suffering from draught conditions.
- 4) **Depletion of Ground Water Resources** :- According to the documentary (Discovery, 2020) 21 Cities will run out of ground water in 2020. Faulty Water management practices is the main cause of the same.
- 5) **Tsunami Floods in Himalayan Region (Uttarakhand)** :- In the June 2013 , due to increase in the temperature and bad urbanization Kedarnath Valley has badly affected series of huge floods which wiped away sacred town of Kedarnath . If we combine Bad development with Effects of Climate change the result is devastating as Shown in Uttarakhand.
- 6) **Floods at Chennai followed by Draught** :- On 1st December 2015 , Chennai , a big metropolitan city was drowned in the floods in a single day rain. The main reason for disaster is ignoring the drainage system of the city in the new development. Construction of the buildings in the run of way of the river choked the Chennai City.Because of this the rising rain water could not able to get the way to drain off to the Bay of Bengal. On December 2nd ,2015 Chennai is officially declared as the disaster zone.After amd year Chennai faced the draught situation for the next two years and in 2017 government had to export water from the other states. The Chennai is now a water less state and the city is declared as dey zero. It is a climate induced water stress .

- 7) **Rising Sea Level – Bay of Bengal :-** Climate change increases the overall temperature of the earth in past decade. As the result the glaciers are melting and the sea level is rising up. An overall water encroachment of 15 feet a year can be observed because of the same. In the case of India the land area of Sundarbans which is acting as carbon sink over these years is reducing in its size because of the sea level is rising . The Island of Ghoramara is reducing to its size and Island of Suparibanga and Island of Ghorachara is totally submersed in sea water .
- 8) **Cyclone hit Orissa:-**On 23rd May 2019 , Cyclone name Fani hit the Orissa coast line . Of the 36 deadliest tropical cyclone in the world 27 Originated on India's Eastern Cost. Orissa timely evacuation saved the human life. According to the film (Discovery, 2020) experts are warning that by 2050 almost 570 coastal cities at risk of flooding due to rise of sea level because climate is changing very fast.
- 9) **Floods of Mumbai :-** In the year 2005 on 26 July , large part of Mumbai was effected by floods , more then 5000 people died . The floods are caused by heaviest recorded 24 – hour rainfall figure of 994 mm . The reason also included the unplanned and old drainage system of Mumbai. Again in the year 2017 the similar conditions are visible and from then this kind of rain is regular in the Mumbai City. The worst is seen in the year 2020 in which the areas which are not affected by floods in past are also drowned.
- 10) **Flash Floods due to melting of Glacier followed by Eartquake at Uttarakhand :-** According to the news article published in Indian Express(warned, 2021)on 8th February , a part of Dehradun - Nanda Devi glacier near chamoli district had broke off and that region was drowned in the floods. Report ((warned, 2021) a researcher named Mohmd. Farooq Azam (Asst. Professor , IIT Indore) expressed that the temperature for ice is from -6 to -20degree centigrade but now it is -2 degree Centigrade , so there is no doubt that this is the resultant of climate change as global temperature is rising thereby melting of the glacier took place. This disaster is followed by earthquake near Prayagraj of magnitude 4.0.

The above mentioned events clearly shows that the climate is changing and it is creating danger to human life and habitat . In all the events above mentioned one thing is common , Unplanned development with the climate change effects had shown the devastating situations and that need to be answered in the near future in order to protect humans and other habitat.

Scope of Built Up Sector :-

According to a report by World Green Building Council , Buildings globally accounts for 30 to 40% of the total energy consumption and 70% of the total electricity consumption. An efficient designed building can largely cut down the operational energy use in its lifetime as compared to the conventional building. Therefore plenty of scope available in the building sector to reduce the global carbon emission and to retard the process of Global Warming.

Around the world Building construction industry is facing three major challenges that are as follows :-

- 1) To minimize the over dependency on the conventional resources for production of the energy . Due to over demand these resources are on the verge of depletion.
- 2) To minimize the environmental damage that can occur due to construction and operational activities. For example air , water , and soil pollution , carbon emission , green house gas emission and other damages to vegetation and natural habitats.
- 3) To select the appropriate material which consumes less embodied energy in manufacturing , and which can be recycled and reduces the carbon emissions thereby reducing the Pollution.

Why & What is Green Buildings:-

Figure 1:- Go Green - Definition of Green Building - www.shutterstock.com

According to the report (Wire, May 16 ,2019) by focusing on energy efficient measures , new building can reduce their energy consumption by 25% and old buildings upto 16 % , further by adopting new green techniques this percentage rises upto 40 % by 2040. Various reports suggests the use of Green Buildings can reduce the Carbon emission and thereby it can contributes in the retardation of the speed of the climate change.According to the report (Pandey, 2014-15) Green Building may be defined as a building whose construction and lifetime of operation assure the healthiest possible environment , while making the most efficient and least disruptive use of land , water , energy and resources. In other words Green Building may be defined as the buildings that are climate responsive and emits less carbon emission as compare to the general structures. The aim of the green building is to minimize the impact on the environment and provide healthy work environment to its users. The following are the key points of Green Building and why we require them for the future are Climate Responsive Architectural Design ; Passive Design Features and Techniques for space heating , cooling , day lighting ; the use of renewable sources of energy ; efficient and environmentally friendly practices during construction ; post occupancy analysis ; the use of vernacular material and techniques for construction and the focus on the health , safety and comfort of the occupants.

The following are the benefits of Using Green Technologies for Buildings:-

Environmental Benefits	Economic Benefits	Social Benefits
Enhance and Protect Biodiversity	Reduce Energy Bills	Enhance Occupants comfort ,health
Improves air and water quality	Reduce water consumption and subsequent load of traditional plants	Improving Aesthetics qualities and improve overall quality of life
Reduce Waste Streams	Enhance marketability	Increase the productivity
Conserve and restore natural resources	Optimize life cycle economic performance	Status Symbol

Table 1:- Benefits of The Green Buildings Source :- Author

In order to encourage green building practices different Green Rating Systems are developed by Green Building Council organization of different countries in order to analyze the performance of the Green Buildings.

Green Building Rating Systems:-According to Author(Sachin, 2012)**Green Building Rating System** or the sustainable building rating system is defined as the tools that analyze the building performance with respect to the standardized parameters and values that allow the comparison with other building. These Rating systems are used by the construction industry in order to provide direct benefits to the users by reducing operational cost. The popularity of these rating systems can be seen in the fact that nearly 400 plus Rating systems are used across the globe . Initially the era of these rating systems started with the development of BREEAM rating systems in 1990 and then with the development of LEED in 2000 these rating systems developed further . The following are the important rating systems discussed in this paper.

- 1) LEED – The Leadership in energy and Environmental Design developed by USGBC (U.S. Green building Council) in 1998 .
- 2) BREEAM – Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (Widely Used in U.K.)
- 3) Green Star – Green Rating System Used In Australia .
- 4) Green Globes .- Green Assessment System Used in Canada
- 5) GRIHA.-Green Rating System Used in India
- 6) GEM – Green rating System newly Introduced in Indian Construction Industry
- 7) LEED INDIA – Widely used in India and Introduced by IGBC

Rating Systems Used across the world :-

1) LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design):-

Developed By :- USGBC(U.S. Green Building Council) Location :- U.S.A.

According to the Report (Birgisdottir, Guide to Sustainability Certification , 2018) LEED certification, developed by the U.S. Green Building Council, is one of the largest existing certification systems. It is inspired by BREEAM and primarily focuses on the environmental and social aspects of building sustainability. Initially it was developed as a pilot project in 1993 and later on its 1st Version was introduced to the construction market in 1998 . According to the report (Sarah, 2019) published by USGBC LEED is the most Famous Rating System across the world. **Around 167 Countries** are following the LEED rating system in the one form or the other. Table 2 shows the number of LEED certified projects in different countries across the world.

Ranking	Countries / Region	Number of Projects	Gross Square Meters (In Millions)
1	Mainland China	1494	68.83
2	Canada	3254	46.81
3	India	899	24.81
4	Brazil	531	16.74
5	Republic of Korea	143	12.15
6	Turkey	337	10.90
7	Germany	327	8.47
8	Mexico	370	8.41
9	China, Taiwan	144	7.30
10	Spain	299	5.81

Table 2: Top 10 Countries Following LEED Rating as Green Building Evaluation System (Sarah, 2019)

Structure of LEED V4.1(U.S.G.B.C.)

S.No.	Parameters	Weightings in Points	Percentage of Weighting
1	Water Efficiency	11	10.00%
2	Integrative Design Approach	1	0.90%
3	Energy and Atmosphere	33	30.00%
4	Indoor Environmental Quality	16	14.54%
5	Environmental Impact	0	0.00%
6	Appropriate Material Selection	13	11.81%
7	Regional Priority	4	3.60%
8	Sustainable Site	10	9.09%
9	Transport	16	14.54%
10	Innovation	6	5.40%
	Total	110	

Table 3:- LEED 4.1 Weightings Source :- USGBC

Accor LEED V4.1 rating system was launched in 2013 and it is the latest green rating system followed in United States of America. The LEED Green Building Rating System is the voluntary consensus based rating system that provide third party verification that a building or community was designed and built to establish energy saving , Water Efficiency , location efficiency , improved indoor environmental quality , stewardship of resources and sensitivity to their impacts. The Structure of these rating system is quite complex and sequential. There are three division in the points system of LEED Rating systems . According to the Figure 2The LEED rating system is divided into 9 Sub Points and that are as follows :-

Figure 2 :- Structure of LEED 4.1 Rating System (Source :- Author)

- 1) **Integrative Process** :- This parameter focused on the integrative working of different experts of the fields (civil , mechanical electrical) in order to achieve maximum benefit for the project.
- 2) **Sustainable Sites** :- Sustainable Site parameter aims at the strategies and techniques of preparing site in order to achieve the maximum benefits out of it. This parameter includes site preparation for pollution prevention to minimize erosion and waterways sedimentation. This parameter also focus on Rain Water Management and reduction of Heat Island Effect. Reduction of light pollution and its impact on site development is also discussed in this parameter . The motive of this parameter is to develop the site in such a way that overall 30% of the total land area should be designed as a open space and out of which 25 % of the area should be vegetated

.Hardscape area should be minimized in order to reduce the heat island effect as well as to reduce the surface runoff and increase the discharge of rain water to the ground.

3) **Material &Resources:-**

This parameter covers LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) of the material selected for building Design , Waste Management , selection of environmental friendly and socially acceptable material. This Parameter also include the idea of optimization of resources by promoting the re-use of existing built up for different functions in order to reduce the footprint. Under this parameter recycle plan and Waste stream audits also incorporated and it also aims at net zero waste generation.

4) **Energy and Atmosphere:-**

The main aim of this parameter is to identify and apply solar and passive design options in order to reduce the use of natural resources to meet the energy demand .It dominantly based on the idea to reduce the ill effects on local climatic condition and also to minimize the contribution towards climate change.

Baseline / Design Case – Benchmarking	Reduce Demand in peak hours	Reduce the Building Footprint and Design Envelope	Increase Efficiency by adopting high efficiency appliances and Solar active and Passive Design Means.	High Performance System	Energy Modelling
---------------------------------------	-----------------------------	---	---	-------------------------	------------------

5) **Location and Transportation:-**

The motive of this parameter is to reduce the cost related to transportation of the material and also reducing the pollution and depletion of the natural resources. According to a report ,Transportation contributes to around 30% of the green house gas emission so that LEED 4.1 encourages the identification of the proper source for the material so that less transportation distance is required to cover. This parameter also focused on the promotion of Electric vehicle as the alternate of the conventional vehicles. High density planning should be preferred so that will reduce the transportation need. The use of Public transport system is favoured under this parameter by reducing the parking facility for individual vehicles.

6) **Indoor Environmental Quality :-** This parameter deals with the comfort conditions which covers air quality , quality of lighting , thermal comfort conditions. This parameter influence the workability and productivity of the occupants of that space and also influence the post occupancy evaluation as it directly affects the health and wellbeing of the occupants. Under this parameter analyses of air changes is done with respect to the number of occupants to provide the User friendly control system for ventilation , thermal comfort and lighting. The control of CO₂ emission and reducing the use of VOC (Volatile Organic Compound) in order to reduce pollution and better air quality to the occupants.

7) **Water Efficiency :-** This parameter deals with the usage of water in a designed building holistically and aims at the Restoration and Recycling of water into portable form . Its aim is to achieve high efficiency in water use as United States of America is the third largest consumers of

water in building operation. Therefore LEED 4.1 addressed this parameter in priority. This parameter further subdivided into Outdoor Water Reduction , Indoor Water Reduction , Cooling Tower and process water use , Water metering.

Indoor Water Use :- According to a report 70% of the daily water used in a building is in indoor spaces. Therefore a benchmarking is done after analysis of the daily usage of the building . LEED 4.1 Suggest that various methods should be adopted so that at least 20% of the reduction should be achieved with respect to this benchmark. It also aims at water conservation and to protect and restore water resources. This is an important parameter as earth contain only 3% of fresh water (Drinkable Water) and out of which 2/3 is trapped in the form glaciers and we need top conserve it.

BREEAM :-

According to (Birgisdottir, Guide to Sustainable Building Certifications, August 2018)BREEAM was the first certification system in the world established in 1990 by BRE (Building Research Establishment) at United Kingdom . Over the year BREEAM undergoes many changes such as in 1998 BREEAM office standards , in 2000 BREEAM for new homes launched , In 2006 codes of sustainability launched and in 2008 post occupancy was introduced as compulsory parameter. In 2011 Introduction of BREEAM new construction to assess all type of new construction buildings and in 2012 BREEAM Refurbished Domestic buildings replace ECO homes and in 2014 both the structures are updated. BREEAM may be defined as the set of standards and certification schemes that measures and certify sustainable values in the built environment.

Figure 3:- Structure of BREEAM rating System (Source :- Author)

- 1. Management :-** This category based on the adoption of sustainable management practices in connection with design , construction , commissioning , handover and aftercare . this parameter is further divided in the following parameters :-
 - Project Brief and Design :-** Task specific Professionals and experts are involved for the Specific roles and responsibilities are defined . Methodologies and process are adopted so check the process is working or not.
 - Life Cycle costing and Service Life Planning :-** Depending on the level of design , designers go in detail for the analysis of life cycle costing to improve the design and to reduce the running cost of the building.
 - Responsible Construction Practices :-** This parameter encourages adoption of the methodology which creates suitable environment for construction and monitoring and which also encourage optimum utilization of the resources and also improve social condition.
- 2. Health and Wellbeing:-**This parameters promotes health , wellbeing, and safety of the building users. In the present COVID- 19 situation this is the most important parameter as it actually gives the scale of the user satisfaction regarding comfort conditions inside the space. Under this parameter the evaluation done on the basis of following parameters:- **Visual Comfort**(6) for evaluation of the space on the basis of lighting quality , **Thermal Comfort** (3) to analyze the indoor temperature and comfort quality , **Indoor Air quality**(4) – to check the air quality by analyzing air exchange ventilation quality inside the space, **Acoustical Performance** (4) – to evaluate the space on the basis of acoustical standards , **Safe and Health Surroundings**(2)- to provide the safe environment in building level as well as site level, **Security**(1):- to check weather building design address the security issues with respect to the region of the site .
- 3. Energy :-** the focus of this process is energy efficiency by adopting procedures and methodology which promotes low carbon emission by adopting solar active and passive design techniques, by selecting efficient cold storage , laboratory and transport system and also by reducing energy demand by using energy efficient equipments.
- 4. Transportation:-**This parameter aimsat the access of the local amenities and sustainable means of transport (Public transport and other means of transport) solution for building users. This parameter also focused on the use of different energy efficient mode of transport systems like Electric vehicles etc.
- 5. Water :-** This parameters focused on the use of water efficient systems which reduces the water consumption in the building operations and also focused on reducing portable water consumption. **Water Consumption**(5) :- aims to reduce the consumption of the portable water through the provision of efficient sanitary fitting , rain water collection and water recycling techniques. **Water Monitoring**(1):- Monitoring of the water use in the building in order to indentify the high usage area and to reduce the water consumption. **Water LeakDetection** (1):- Reducing the water wastage by identification of the water leakage spots. **Water EfficientEquipment** (1):- Reducing water consumption by water efficient system.

- 6. Material :-** This category focused on material selection which reduces the environmental and social impact of construction products used in construction. The life cycle assessment approach is adopted which include the consideration of impact during manufacturing , design , procurement , installation , in use and end of life . The parameter focused on Environmental impact , responsible sourcing and product durability. This parameter is further divided in following parameters :- **Environmental Impact from construction product – Building Life Cycle Assessment (Upto 7) :-** Reducing the impact of Building Life Cycle process and integrating the outcome in the design decision process. **Environmental impact from construction product – Environmental Product Declaration (EDP) (1):-** Encourage the availability of Comparable data on impact of construction product. **Responsible Sourcing of Construction product (4) :-** Recognizing and encouraging responsible sourcing of construction product. **Designing for durability and Resilience (1):-** Increase the life span of the building by designing for durability and protection from degradation by selection of appropriate material. **Material Efficiency (1):-** Reduction of Environmental Impact through optimizing the use of material during all stages of construction.
- 7. Waste :-** This parameter focused on reduction of the waste minimization through optimized design methods which focus on the minimum waste generation during the process of construction and life time of the building. This parameter is further divided in **Construction Waste Management(5):-** Developing resource management plan during the process of demolition in order to recover material in the usable form. **Use of recycle and Sustainably sourced aggregate (1) :-** Encouraging the use of recycled and secondary aggregate with lower environmental impact. **Operational Waste (1):-**Encouraging segregation and storage of Recyclable waste. **Speculative Finishes(1) :-** floor and ceiling finishes installed in show area only in order to reduce waste. **Adaptation to climate change (1):-** Implementation of measures to mitigate the impact of climate change over the life span of the building. **Design for disassembly and adaptability (2) :-** Implementation of measures of disassembly and adaptability to provide flexibility to use the building over its life span of time.
- 8. Landuse and Ecology :-** This Parameter encourages the sustainable development approach which leaves the biodiversity in the better state then before. The subparts of this parameter are :- **Site Selection (1) :-** the reuse of the previously used and contaminated land for e.g. reuse of Brownfield sites .**Ecological Risks and Opportunity (Upto 2):-** identification of risks and opportunity . **Managing impacts on ecology (upto 3):-** methodology adopted to avoid impact on site . **Ecological change and enhancement (up to 4)** steps taken to enhance site ecology . **Long term ecological management and maintenance(up to 2) :-** Encouraging long term maintenance and management plan to improve ecological development .
- 9. Pollution :-** This category control the pollution and surface runoff of the building’s location and use. The aim of this parameter is to reduce the impact of the building over surrounding communities and environment. **Impact of Refrigerants (3):-** the aim is to give rewards to the building which showcase the less impact of the Refrigerants. **Local air quality (up to 2):-** the focus is to identify the design which limit their impact on local air quality. **Flood and**

surface water management (5):-aim is to reward the building which shows the reduced impact because of off site and on site flooding. **Reduction of Night time light pollution (1)** :- aim is to reduce the night time pollution through careful design and specification of light source. **Reduction of Noise pollution (1)**:-reducing the impact of external noise from the building.

10. Innovation :- focused on rewarding the innovative solution and design approach. (up to 2)

Green Star Rating Systems (1.3):-

Figure 4:- Structure of Green Star Rating System (Source : Author)

Launched in Australia in 2003 by the **Green Building Council of Australia (GBCA)**. The Green Star rating system assesses the sustainability of projects at all stages of the building life cycle. According to the Official Website of Green Star state that around 950 projects are certified using Green Star Rating system .The research found that, on average, Green Star-certified buildings produce 62% fewer greenhouse gas emissions and use 66% less electricity than average Australian buildings. Green Star buildings use 51% less potable water than average buildings. Green Star-certified buildings also have been found to recycle 96 per cent of their construction and demolition waste, compared to the average 58% for new construction projects. There are many versions of Green star launched the latest version is GREEN STAR 1.3. After observing the structure of the Green Star Certification system it was found that few important parameters are merged with the other parameter like Waste etc. The following are the Parameters of Green Star Rating systems :-

1. Management :- This category based on the adoption of sustainable management practices in connection with design , construction , commissioning , handover and aftercare . This

- parameter is further divided into – **Green Star Accredited Professions (1):-**focused o involving the professionals for the task of rating
2. **Indoor Environmental Quality:-**this parameter reward initiatives that enhance the comfort and well-being of occupants. The credits within this category address issues such as air quality, thermal comfort and acoustic comfort.
 3. **Energy :-** aims to reduce overall greenhouse emissions from operations by addressing energy demand reduction, use efficiency and generation from alternative sources.
 4. **Transportation :-** aims at reduction on the dependency of private car use as an important means of reducing overall greenhouse gas emissions, as well as to encourage the provision of alternative forms of transportation.
 5. **Water :-** this parameter is to encourage and reward initiatives that reduce the consumption of potable water through measures such as the incorporation of water efficient fixtures and building systems and water re-use.
 6. **Material :-** Aims to address the consumption of resources for the project, by encouraging the selection of low-impact materials.
 7. **Land use and Ecology :-** this is to reduce the negative impacts on sites' ecological value as a result of urban development and reward projects that minimise harm and enhance the quality of local ecology.
 8. **Emission:-**Aims to assess the environmental pollution generated by projects and its impact and reduce their effects on the atmosphere, watercourse and native animals.
 9. **Innovation:-** this parameter is to promote the strategies that promote built environment.

Green Globes Rating System :-

Figure 5:- Structure of Green Globes Rating System (Source : Author)

Green Globes is a online Building Rating System ,adopted in Canada and U.S.A. This is a flexible rating system as this gives liberty to the designer to use “ Not Applicable” for certain criteria that may not be relevant to project because of the regional parameter this which removes the question from the survey without penalty. Green Globes assessment can be divided in 4 stages that basically based on the building design and its development through different stages. Green Globes Design is intended to guide the project through the project delivery stages using the integrated design approach. This is a questionnaire based assessment system.

Green Building Rating Systems in India The green building in India started with the established of the IGBC in 2001 , which was an initiative of confederation of Indian Industry (CII) along with the World Green Building Council and USGBC. The green movement started with 20000 sq Ft. in 2004 with the first green building in India, **CII- Sohrabji Godrej Green Business Centre in Hyderabad** was inaugurated on 14 July 2004. By the end of 2013 India had more then 1.28 billion sq. Ft. of green building area (IGBC data). According to the Reports published in The Hindu (Dated 30 March 2018) the Indian Green building market may be double and will reach to around 10 Million Sq.Ft by the end of 2022. in the adoption of the green rating systems for the building . There are majorly three Green Building Rating system in India. That are **LEED , GRIHA , GEM and IGBC**.

GEM Rating System :- Green and Eco Friendly Movement is the new Green Building rating system in India. It was introduced by ASSOCHAM. This is a new introduced Building Rating System in India introduced on 13 January 2019 at Jaipur. This Building evaluation system works on two types of Parameters one is Essential Parameters and 2) is the rating Parameters. These rating parameters focuses on different parameters like water efficiency , energy efficiency etc . This Rating Systems comprises of 30 Principles out of which 4 are Essential and 26 are Rating Parameters.This is the only Rating System which had introduced Parking as a Essential Parameter and as we can see the structure of the Rating System we realize that the GEM Rating system is the simple and easily understood by the designers as well as common man. ASSOCHAM had tried to reduce the complexity of the rating system. The Essential parameter includes 1)

Figure 6:- Structure of GEM Rating System (Source : Author)

Government Approved Plans :- This is the essential process as the project had followed all the norms and bye – laws are needed to be checked before green rating evaluation starts. **2)Fire and Life Safety in Sustainable Buildings :-**The building design should be as per NBC Code 2016 and the building should be given NOC (No Objection Certificate) by local development authority . **3)Construction Management best Practices :-** the aim of this parameter to minimize the hazardous effects of construction on existing soil condition , existing trees , microclimate and drainage system and follow best management practice during construction and follow soil erosion control from project site.

4) Parking for Building Occupants :- the project must have fulfilled the parking requirements as per local government byelaws. The rest 26 Principal are for rating and the major categories are as follows :-

S.No.	Parameters	Weightings in Points	Percentage of Weighting
1	Water Efficiency	23	17.70%
2	Waste Management	8	6.15%
3	Energy Efficiency	28	21.53%
4	Air Quality	9	7.00%
5	Environmental Impact	4	3.00%
6	Appropriate Material Selection	28	21.53%
7	Project management	M	M
8	Site Management	7	5.38%
9	Transport	3	2.30%
10	Innovation	5	3.84%

Table 4:- Weightings of GEM Rating System (Source :- GEM)

- 1) **Water Efficiency** :- This Rating system focused on the percentage of the rainwater collected in daily rainfall. The point vary from 60% to 90 % collection of the daily rain water . To encourage the reduction of water loss , The rating system has prioritize the use of Sensor based appliances rather than the conventional one. Further the Recycling of Grey water and the reuse of it in flushing and other utilities is also given priority. This system focus on the recycling of the maximum grey water collected and reuse of the same in the form of flushing.
- 2) **Energy Efficiency** :- In GEM and in other rating systems Energy efficiency has given top most priority. This is the first rating system in which solar passive design techniques are given more priority in order to get best practice for energy efficiency parameter. The use of renewable energy through the means of solar cell and wind mill is given more priority. The focus of these rating system is to provide adequate freedom to designers to encourage the use of day lighting in order to reduce the consumption of electricity in the day time.
- 3) **Appropriate Material Selection and Use** :-This parameter focus on the appropriate material selection for the building design and for construction , which reduces the burden of waste generation and also it should be environmental friendly and Recyclable. The major stress of these rating system is to encourage the use of local material which could be reuse easily in other form . The local material will make the designers building more climate responsive.
- 4) **Waste Management** :- the overall focus of this parameter is to minimize the waste production during construction and operation of the building . This parameter deals with the post occupancy waste production and onsite organic waste conversion to nutrient rich product .
- 5) **Air Quality** :- This parameter deals with the quality of air we breathe. In todayspendimic situation this is the most important parameter as the

GRIHA Rating

Figure 7:- Structure of GRIHA Rating System (Source :- Author)

Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment is an Indian Green Rating System Introduced in India in the year 2007 developed by TERI (The Energy and Research Institute. In 2019 GRIHA revised the rating system and completely come up a new version with New parameters etc. The new Inclusion in the rating system is Life Cycle Costing analysis. This is the first Indian Rating system which adopted this important parameter as majority of the global and other Indian rating systems haven't really focused to get this parameter on board.

Percentile threshold	Achievable stars as per GRIHA v.2019
25-40	★
41-55	★★
56-70	★★★
71-85	★★★★
86 and more	★★★★★

Table 5:- State wise Status of LEED Rated Project

System :-

GRIHA -Green Rating for Integrated Habitat Assessment is an Indian Green Rating System

LEED In India :-

According to report (GBCI, 2020) GBCI released the top 10 States of India using LEED as Green Rating System for building evaluation and Certification. According to the Report Released by GBCI , Maharashtra is the state which have maximum Green Build upspace of 10258564 Sq. M. followed by Karnataka and others. We can easily see in the table Maharashtra topping the list with maximum projects .

Ranking	States / Region	Number of Projects	Gross Sq. Meters	Climatic Zone.
1	Maharashtra	373	10258564	Warm & Humid , Hot & Dry Composite
2	Karnataka	301	9691621	Warm & Humid , Composite
3	Haryana	139	5906220	Composite
4	Tamil Nadu	178	5405415	Warm & Humid, Cold
5	Uttar Pradesh	95	4756050	Composite
6	Telangana	106	4143928	Composite , Warm & Humid
7	Delhi	72	3074542	Composite
8	Gujarat	57	2247419	Hot & Humid
9	West Bengal	40	1986383	Warm & Humid
10	Rajasthan	21	901918	Composite & Hot & Dry

LEED Rating System :- Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design is Introduced in India (IGBC, 2016) in the year 2001 with the formation of IGBC- Indian Green Building Council. This is the most adopted Building rating system not only in India but abroad as well . As we have seen in all the rating system (Global , Indian) Energy Efficiency is the primary concern. As we have seen in GEM as well as in GRIHA – Water Conservation is in the second priority , But in Global rating system we have Waste Management and other parameters preferred over water conservation. LEED introduced by IGBC in India is quite simple in structure as compared to the LEED rating system adopted by USGBC. Here Transport and regional priority parameter is missing.

Parameters	Points
Sustainable Architecture & Design	5
Site Selection and planning	14
Water Conservation	18
Energy Efficiency	28
Building material and Resources	16
Indoor Environmental Quality	12
Innovation and Development	7

Certification Level	Points	Recognition
Certified	50-59	Good Practice
Silver	60-69	Best Practice
Gold	70-79	Outstanding Performance
Platinum	80-89	National Excellence
Super Platinum	90-100	Global Leadership

Figure 8:- Certification Points LEED - INDIA (IGBC, 2016)

Findings&Conclusion :-

On Comparative analysis of global as well as Indian rating system we can easily see that all the Rating system have some common parameters such as (Energy Efficiency , Water Efficiency , Waste Management , Selection of Material , Site management Air Quality / Comfort etc. It is also a meter of Observation that these rating system had variation in terms of Weightings and this variation in rating systems are region specific as well.

India have three different rating systems LEED – India , GRIHA , GEM and after observing these rating systems even these rating systems also have variation in the weighting of the parameter. In India Energy Efficiency and Water Efficiency are the most important parameter therefore these rating all the above mentioned rating system have maximum weightings for these parameters.

It is also observed that there are some parameters which are not included in some of the rating systems and that are Environmental Impact / Pollution / Emission and Transportation etc . The fire safety and Security is the important parameter which is not included by all the rating systems except GEM Rating system of India. On comparative analysis of these rating systems it was found that Indian Rating Systems are not answering some of the important issues like Transport issue and Environmental Impact assessment which is very much important in case of assessment of Buildings.

1) Comparative Analysis of Global Rating System with Indian Rating System :-

S.No.	Parameters	GRIHA 2019	LEED	GEM	GREEN GLOBES	BREEM 2018	GREEN Star	LEED 4.1V
	Nation	INDIA	INDIA	INDIA	Canada and U.S.	U.K.	Australia	U.S.
	Total Points	100	100	130	1000	100	100	110
1.	Water Efficiency Recycle and Reuse	16	18	23	110		22	11
	Percentage	16%	18%	17.7%	11%	7%	22%	10%
2	Waste Management	7	12	8	32	6	N.C.	0
	Percentage	7%	12%	6.15%	3.2%	6%		0
3	Energy Efficiency	18	28	28	395	16	24	33
	Percentage	18%	28%	21.53%	39.5%	16%	24%	30%
4	Indoor Air Quality	12	12	9	150	14	12	16
	Percentage	12%	12%	7.0%	15%	14%	12%	14.54%
5	Environmental Impact Pollution Emission/Parameters	0	0	4	82.5	8	7	0
	Percentage	0	0	3.0%	8.25%	8%	7%	0
6	Appropriate Material Selection	12	16	28	93	15	10	13
	Percentage	12%	16%	21.53%	13%	15%	10%	11.81%
7.	Project Management	4	0	(M)	37.5	11	10	0

	Percentage	4%	0	N.A.	3.75%	11%	10%	0
8.	Site Management	12	14	7	120	13	7	10
	Percentage	12%	14%	5.38%	12%	13%	7%	9.09%
9	Transport	0	0	3	N.C.S.		8	16
	Percentage	0	0	2.30%		10%	8%	14.54%
10	Innovation	5	7	5		10		6
	Percentage	5%	7%	3.84%		10%		5.4%

Table 6:-Comparative Analysis of Indian & Global Green Rating System

Climate Change is the biggest threat to the world. In last decade we have seen in the increase in the number of natural disasters that is because of the climate change. Building Industry is therefore focusing on Green Structures to make the building more climate responsive and to contribute in order to the retard the speed at which climate is changing. Our rating systems are not incorporating these changing climatic conditions. On comparative study of these Green Rating Systems, It was observed that Safety and Security is completely ignored in all the rating systems .

All rating system should also include Fire Safety as a important parameter as comprises on these issues may lead to a big accident like Grenfell tower . Single rating system may give errors for the same building in different climatic zones , and because of the same we will not get proper result of the analysis , therefore it is recommended to have rating system flexible and should have local parameter according to the local climatic zone. In order to select proper and appropriate material for the building Life Cycle Assessment and Costing can be incorporated in the building rating systems. Seismic Design Consideration should also be the part of Green Building rating system as we cannot compromise building safety and security to achieve sustainability.

References :-

1. Abhishek Rana, D. B. (2016). Methodology for Developing Criteria for Green Building Rating Tool for Gujarat State . *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* , 843-849.
2. Awasthi, R. (2016). Green Building Rating System In India and studying the long term effectiveness of green building . *IRJMST* .
3. Binh K.Nguyen, H. A. (2011). Comparative Review of Five Sustainable Rating System. *2011 International Conference on Green Building and Sustainable Cities* (pp. 376-386). ELSEVIER.
4. Birgisdottir, K. G. (2018). *Guide to Sustainability Certification* . Published by SBi and GXN.

5. Birgisdottir, K. G. (August 2018). *Guide to Sustainable Building Certifications*. the Danish Building Research Institute , 3XN Architects (GXN). SBI , GXN.
6. Broschure, C. (n.d.). CASBEE Rating System .
7. Bruno Lee, M. T. (2011). Embodied energy of Building material and Green Building Rating system –A case study of Industrial Halls . *ELSEVIER* , 67-71.
8. Cardace Say, A. W. (2008). Sustainable rating Systems the World . *CTBUH - Council of Tall Building and urban Habitat* , 18-29.
9. Cassandra L. Champagne, C. B. (2016). Assessing the Resilience of LEED Certified Green Buildings . *International Conference on Sustainable Design , Engineering and Construction* (pp. 380-387). ELSEVIER.
10. Chaturvedi, A. A. (2020). *Structure of BREEAM Rating System* .
11. Chaturvedi, A. A. *Structure of Green Globes Rating System* .
12. Cheatham, C. (2011). *First LEED platinum Building at Risk of Collapse* .
www.greenbuildinglawupdate.com.
13. Cladding used to make Grenfell Tower a ' Green Building ' may have accelerated spread of fire , 1 (Published in The Guardian Jun 16, 2017).
14. Devarshi Tathagat, D. R. (2015). Role of Green Building in Sustainable Construction – Need , Challenges and Scope in the Indian Scenario . *IOSR -Journal for Mechanical and Civil Engineering* , 1-9.
15. Dr. M.N. Hedao, M. S. (2016). A comparative Analysis of Rating System in Green Building . *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)* , 1393- 1399.
16. GBCA. (2013). *The Value of Green Star* . GBCA.
17. GBCI. (2020, January 2020). *Maharastra Rank 1st in GBCI India's List of Top 10 States for LEED in India*. Retrieved June 07, 2020, from www.constructionworld.in:https://www.constructionworld.in/Latest-Construction-News/Maharashtra-ranks-1st-in-GBCI-India%E2%80%99s-list-of-Top-10-States-for-LEED-in-India/22985
18. GERMANWATCH. (2019, December 10). *Climate Change Performance Index*. Retrieved June 13, 2020, from www.Climate-Change-Performance-Index.org: <https://www.climate-change-performance-index.org/>
19. GRIHA. (2019). *GRIHA 2019 ABRIDGED MANUAL*. GRIHA & TERI.
20. Gupta, K. (2009). *TOWARD SUSTAINABLE DESIGN -THE EXCLUDED ISSUES LEED RATING SYSTEM IN INDIA*. Pennsylvania : The Pennsylvania State University.
21. Guylaine Desmarais, R. T. (2010). *Why do Green Building Enclosure fail and what can be done about it*. ASHRAE.
22. Hua, G. B. (2009). Integration Green Building Rating System with Building Information Modeling using cost based fuzzy Logic Decision Rules . *Handbook of research on Building Information Modeling and Construction informatics Concepts and Technologies* , 1- 12.
23. IGBC. (2016). *GREEN NEW BUILDING RATING SYSTEM version 3.0*. Hyderabad: IGBC.
24. Jain, A. N. *Certified Green Building* . Jaipur.

25. Jernej Markelj, M. K. (2014). A Simplified Method for Evaluating Building Sustainability in the Early design phase for Architect . *Sustainability* , 8775-8794.
26. Lascher, B. (2017, Jun 14). *Pacific Standard*. Retrieved Jun 29, 2020, from www.psmg.com: <https://psmag.com/environment/disaster-resilience-part-of-sustainability-too-40935>
27. Lau, Z. G. Post Occupancy evaluation of the Thermal environment in a green building., (p. 357). Hongkong.
28. Luis Braganca, R. m. (2010). Building Sustainability assessment. *Sustainability* , 2010-2023.
29. Menon, M. (2014, October 11). Green Rated buildings not keeping their promise , says CSE r. *The Hindu* .
30. Mohd. Ahmed, M. A. (2016). World Green Building Rating System : A Comparative Study. *International conference cum exhibition on Building Utilities 2016*. New Delhi : Department of Mechanical Engineering ,Jamia Milia Islamia.
31. Mr. Rohan V. Nalawade, D. S. (2016). Comparative Review criteria utilization by LEED and GRIHA : Green building rating system for new construction in India. *International Journal of Science and Research Publication* , 416-419.
32. Pandey, Shradha. (2016). Impact of Green Building Rating Systems on the Sustainability and efficiency of Green Buildings case analysis of Malaysia. *Malaysua Sustainable City Program* , 1- 25.
33. Pandit, A. S. *Against LEED : Does LEED matter anymore ?* www.arch2o.com.
34. Rawat, D. (2019). *GEM Sustainability Certification Rating Program - Points List* . New Delhi : ASSOCHAM.
35. Retno Rahardjati, D. F. (2011). Green Building rating system : The need of Material Resource Criteria. *International Conference on Environmental, Science and Technology (ICEST- 2011)* (pp. 148-151). ICEST.
36. Richard Reed, A. B. (2009). International Comparison of Sustainable Rating Tool. *JOSRE- Vol 1* , 1-22.
37. Sachin, V. G. (2012). Comparative Study of Rating system for Green Building in Developing and Developed Countries. *The International Conference on Construction in Developing Countries* . Bangkok: ICCIDC-III.
38. Sarah, S. (2019, February 13). *U.S. Green Building Council announces Top 10 Countries and Regions for LEED Green Building*. Retrieved June 7, 2020, from www.usgbc.org: <https://www.usgbc.org/articles/us-green-building-council-announces-top-10-countries-and-regions-leed-green-building>
39. Schnabel, R. a. (2013). Will LEED Survive in Asia ? *47 International Conference of Architectural Science Association* (pp. 385-394). Australia : The Architectural Science Association (ANZA ScA).
40. Sergio E Palmere, C. E. (2015). Integration of Energy and Fire Prevention system in Green Building . *Journal of Energy and Power Engineering* , 1-8.
41. Sharad R.Khese, M. H. (2016). A Comparative Study of Rating System In Green Building . *International journal of Engineering Research* , 134- 136.

42. Udelson, J. (2009). *Appendix - Green Building rating System around the world* . New York : SEED , International Council of Shopping Centers.
43. Usman Aminu Umar, H. T. (2012, December). Retrieved May Saturday , 2020, from www.researchgate.net:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233996916_Impact_of_Environmental_Assessment_of_Green_Building_Materials_on_Sustainable_Rating_System
44. Usman Aminu Umar, H. T. (2011). *Impact of Environmental Assessment of Green Building Material on Sustainable Rating System*.
45. Veronica Soebarto, D. N. (2010). Rethinking the adoption of Green building Rating system in Developing countries. *International Conference on sustainable Environmental Architecture* , (pp. v1 - v12). indonesia.
46. Virendra Kanaujia, A. S. (2017). Comparative Review of Indian Green Building Rating System . *Journal of Energy Research and EnvironmentalTechnology* , 194-198.
47. Wayne B. Trusty, M. ., *Integrating LCA Tools in Green Building Rating Systems*. ATHENA.
48. Wholey, F. (2015). Building Resilience : A Framework for Assessing and Communicating the Cost and Benefit of Resilient Design Strategies . *Perkins+will Reserach Journal* , 7-18.
49. Wikipedia. (n.d.). *Philip Merrill Environmental Center*. Retrieved from www.wikipedia.org:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philip_Merrill_Environmental_Center